

Metabolic, immunological and lifestyle factors associated with different phenotypes of obesity and their correlation with weight changes in children in Latvia.

Version 1

Description

Obesity in pediatric population has reached pandemic extents and its prevalence continues to expand worldwide in the last decades, and this disease is defined as one of the most serious public health challenges of the 21st century for a valid reason. Obesity not only reduces life quality and lifespan, but also significantly increases risk of developing metabolic and cardiovascular diseases in childhood and adulthood, as well as impairs child's immune system with subsequent risk of infectious, autoimmune and oncological diseases. Importantly, that according to the latest study, prevalence of overweight and obesity in Latvia was found to be 21.9% for boys and 19.9% for girls among children aged 7 years and 29.1% for boys and 24.8% for girls among 9 years old schoolchildren.

Children with obesity could be classified in two phenotypes – metabolically healthy obesity (MHO) and metabolically unhealthy obesity phenotype (MUO) according to the consensus-based definition. Depending on the individual phenotype, young patients have variable prognosis for the time of development and severity of cardiovascular and metabolic complications, as well as severity of infectious and autoimmune diseases, and subsequent quality of life and lifespan in adulthood.

There is limited research in the paediatric population and no research in Latvia for adipose tissue inflammatory phenomenon and its correlation with metabolic, immunological state, lifestyle related and other risk factors. There is no nationally representative data describing which factors are the most crucial in determining MHO and MUO phenotype in children and adolescence. Obesity prevalence significantly rises in pre-puberty and puberty age in the paediatric population, especially among children over 10

years of age. There is a high possibility that, for example, due to pre-puberty and puberty changes, lifestyle or other factor impact, MHO phenotype could crossover to MUO phenotype. Considering higher risk of immunometabolic disturbances and higher malignancy risk in individuals with MUO phenotype, that would be essential to determine phenotype determining risk factors and the impact of weight loss in terms of early intervention and prevention measures.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

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Researchers

Lauma Springe (0000-0001-7681-9184), Amanda Marija Jundase (0009-0009-0562-1993), Jurgita Gailite (0000-0001-8191-0687), Jana Pavare (0000-0001-8469-4713), Aļona Lavrenova (0009-0004-5137-240X), Kristine Vaivode (0009-0002-0192-2827), Anna Gutmane (0009-0005-1917-7601), Iveta Dzivite Krisane (0000-0002-3045-7904)

Organizations
Riga Stradiņš University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Metabolic, immunological and lifestyle factors associated with different phenotypes of obesity and their correlation with weight changes in children in Latvia.

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Contact: Pavāre Jana (jana.pavare@rsu.edu.lv), Lavrenova Aļona (034480@rsu.edu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: IZP-2024/1-0252

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Restricted

4. Templates

Descriptions

RSU DMP Template

Primary data:

Data Management Plan | Metabolic, immunological and lifestyle factors associated with different phenotypes of obesity and their correlation with weight changes in children in Latvia. CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 05/02/2025

- Interview data obtained by patient and their parent interview, questionnaires, Data is necessary for obtaining data about prenatal and postnatal data, onset of weight problems, screen time, sleep duration, type 2 diabetes risk in family, hyperphagia, quality of life and depression, which is needed to evaluate potential factors in determining different obesity phenotypes;

- Clinical data, obtained by determining anthropometric parameters, sexual maturation stage, performing bioimpedance analysis, 6 minute walk test, echocardiography. Data is needed to determine obesity phenotypes and overall health state as well as analyze these parameter differences among phenotypes;

- Laboratory data, including cardiometabolic parameters, immunometabolic inflammation parameters. Data is necessary to determine obesity phenotype, analyse possible differences between immunometabolic inflammation and cardiometabolic state among different phenotypes .

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Data observed in this project is highly relevant to achieve objectives of the study. Collected data will be used to:

- Estimate prevalence of metabolically healthy obesity and metabolically unhealthy obesity phenotypes in children in Latvia;
- Compare initial sociodemographic, anthropometric parameters and other clinical data, baseline laboratory parameters of cardiovascular health and glucose metabolism in children among different obesity phenotypes;

- Analyze the differences between metabolically healthy and metabolically unhealthy obesity in children in association with immunometabolic inflammation of adipose tissue, lifestyle and other risk factors;
- Evaluate association of weight changes with immunometabolic inflammation status, lifestyle-related and other factors after a 6-month period in both obesity phenotypes in children.

Data will be collected using the results of the patient's clinical examination and tests, including laboratory analysis, interview data of patients and their parents, internationally validated questionnaires.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Our study results will provide an important understanding of childhood obesity at all project stages, and study dataset and our study team is indented to capture all interested audiences including national and local authorities, as well as the public sector.

Obtained data would certainly be important to identify preventable obesity risk factors for children and adolescents, as this would help to establish weight correction and prevention programs in Latvia. These programs would not only provide recommendations on healthy lifestyles and physical activities, but would also educate parents, physicians, and society in general.

Project dataset could be used for creation of educational programs for public together with Disease Prevention and Control Center of Latvia on the care of children with obesity and educational materials for patients with obesity; developing special clinical algorithms and clinical pathways ensuring the continuity of unified care, follow-up, and treatment of children with obesity; developing informative brochures for primary care specialists on the aetiology, investigation, and treatment of childhood obesity. Obtained dataset will provide unique and fundamental data for further studies and serve as basis for

development of clinical algorithms to improve management of childhood obesity not only in Latvia, but also internationally.

The results and data obtained in this project will lay the ground for further research activities and new project applications aiming to: (1) investigate the potential causes of adipose tissue (AT) immune cell infiltration and activation; (2) explore the role of adipocytes in promotion of and interaction with AT immune cells; (3) identify the protective factors preserving MHO profile; (4) investigate protective factors preventing the crossover of MHO to the metabolically unhealthy obese; (5) develop targeted preventive approaches, immunological therapies potentially targeted to adipocytes, and other precision medicine strategies for children with obesity.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Clinical data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- SAV

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

4.5 GB

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

No

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

-

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Codebook

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

-

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Expected formats are .SAV and .CSV. .SAV could be used with IBM SPSS Statistics, but .CSV format is accessible with widely used software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

IBM SPSS Statistics - Comprehensive statistical analysis and data management

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

SSK classification

We will use SSK classification by mentioning diagnosis names that are coded in SSK classification. In this project we will not use uncommon or project specific ontologies or vocabularies.

2.2.5 Other relevant remarks

-

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

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2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Access will be provided by request access, request with collaboration proposal could be send to the authors.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2028-01-03

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2028-01-03

3 years

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

-

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

Storage

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

Costs are covered by RSU.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data?

RSU

Not applicable

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Jana Pavare (0000-0001-8469-4713)
- Aļona Lavrenova (0009-0004-5137-240X)

3.1.5 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

Our data security measures will include restricted access, which will be available only for research team members, and in case in any changes in team group, the access to the database could be changed. Team members signed official documents against dissemination to third persons. Data encryption and anonymization will be applied – no personal and/or sensitive data will be used and stored in database.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research?

During research data will be stored and analyzed by using Google disc drive, IBM SPSS, and double database storage at researchers personal data storage. All storage places would be secured with restricted access, passwords, strict data access control. The data recovery options also will be applied. Database data will not include personal or sensitive data.

3.2.4 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long term preservation and curation

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

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3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data?

No

3.3.5 Will data collected/generated include sensitive information?

No

3.3.6 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

Other

Collected/generated data will not include sensitive information

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